

Revamping the Diploma in Chemical Engineering Curriculum: Issues and Challenges

Sin-Moh Cheah

School of Chemical & Life Sciences, Singapore Polytechnic, Singapore

smcheah@sp.edu.sg

Abstract

The desired attributes for chemical engineering graduates today have changed fundamentally. Apart from having to deal with deeper and wider knowledge bases, graduates faced increasing process complexity in their working environments. The focus at the workplace can now be very broad, involving engineers in highly integrated multidisciplinary team-based industrial projects, requiring a range of skill sets beyond traditional technical areas. This paper firstly summarizes the significant developments in chemical engineering most pertinent in this context. Secondly, it summarizes the experience of the author in executing a curriculum innovation to re-engineer a Diploma in Chemical Engineering to prepare students for such changing demands using the CDIO framework. The need to introduce chemical product design as a fundamental shift away from classical process plant design, as well as the systematic infusion of “generic transferable skills” such as teamwork, communication, and a range of creative and critical thinking skills were discussed.

Keywords: Chemical engineering, curriculum revamp, CDIO, chemical product design.

1 The changing chemical engineering curriculum

Chemical engineering as a discipline on its own is relatively young, starting with the integration of industrial chemistry and physics into an engineering science [1]. As a discipline, chemical engineering has constantly evolved to meet the demand of the chemical process industries [2], [3]. As we moved into the new millennium, the industries, which include the petroleum, fine chemicals, pharmaceuticals and health, cosmetics, household care, food, environment and electronics sectors, have been facing dramatic social, economic and technical challenges, on a global and local scale. Globalization, for example, has brought about rapid changes in businesses and technologies, resulting in companies making deep and rapid changes in the scope of their activities and the strategies adopted to remain profitable and achieve sustainable growth. Such changes also affected the way they view the chemical engineering profession.

With advances made in life sciences, information technology, green chemistry and nanotechnologies, just to name a few, many of the chemical products of today and

tomorrow do not have much in common with those of twenty years ago. The portfolio of skills and technical knowledge required by chemical engineers has also changed tremendously. Chemical engineering education has also evolved over the years to keep up with the new reality. New paradigm appears as the profession responded to the various changes affecting it [4]. Various authors had put forward their views on chemical engineering of the future [5]-[9].

Responding to the needs of chemical industries, leading educational governing bodies carried out extensive curricular review and called for education revamp, for example the US Accreditation Board for Engineering and Technology (ABET), UK's Institution of Chemical Engineers (IChemE), and the European Federation of Chemical Engineering Working Party on Education (EFCE-WPE). The Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT) similarly hosted conducted workshops under the banner of its Frontiers in Chemical Engineering Education initiative [10].

However, most of the suggestions for curriculum changes were targeted at technical coverage of the new knowledge needed, with heavy emphasis on biology, molecular science, multi-scale analysis and systems approach to processes and engineering systems, plus references to the need to introduce product design [11]-[14]. Although some mention was made on the need to teach what the IChemE called “general transferable skills” of teamwork, communication, etc, there still lacked a solid framework on how this can be infused into the chemical engineering curriculum. It is therefore not surprising that the study report from the World Chemical Engineering Council [15], which was based on a survey of 2,158 young chemical engineers in 63 different countries, and highlighted these shortcomings in chemical engineers.

Today, most organizations fill their knowledge gaps by utilizing cross-functional decision-making teams. To be an engineer means being involved in customer satisfaction, research, product development, process and manufacturing controls, and marketing [16]. The background knowledge that chemical engineers need to have differs considerably in some ways from that of ‘classically’ educated process engineers [17]. For example, a chemical engineer may be a member of the original new concept team and stay with a product throughout the entire development cycle, throughout its service life and right through to material recycling.

The broad-based nature of chemical engineering education is also increasingly being appreciated by a wide range of industries. Recent chemical engineering graduates

now found employment in industries that did not exist 10-20 years ago or did not until recently discover the usefulness and relevance of chemical engineers in their profession [18]. New opportunities had opened up for chemical engineers in new areas such as pharmaceuticals, biotechnology, nanotechnology, product development, and sustainable development [19]. Recently, Bryne [20] reported that “there is an increasing demand among employers for graduates who possess not only technical competencies, but also a range of the so-called ‘soft’ skills or ‘higher order’ skills; skills such as communication, presentation, teamworking, leadership, and so on . . .”.

Lin [21] noted that in addition to the traditional role of developing, operating and optimizing chemical and physical processes to transform raw materials into products for the enrichment of the quality of life, the expanded role now include promoting and exploiting the applications of new scientific advances to benefit mankind as well as the application of related knowledge to achieve sustainability and harmony for the world environment.

The Course Management Team (CMT) in Singapore Polytechnic long recognized the need to also revamp its 3-year Diploma in Chemical Engineering (DCHE) program. It was the seminal paper on chemical product design by Moggridge and Cussler [22] and adoption of the CDIO Initiative by the Polytechnic that provided the CMT with a desired framework that is long sought after to form the basis for its curriculum revamp. CDIO stands for Conceive, Design, Implement, Operate, the brainchild of collaboration between MIT and 3 universities in Sweden, namely Chalmers University of Technology, Linköping University, and Royal Institute of Technology (KTH) [23]. The CDIO framework comes in a 4-Part Syllabus and 13 skill sets, supported by 12 Standards. Each program can customize the syllabus to fit the program needs [24].

2 Diploma in Chemical Engineering curriculum revamp

The approach towards curriculum revamp undertaken is from the ‘top down’, starting with key graduate attributes. This is because it has been reported that curriculum designed in this manner, is an effective ‘systems approach’ to providing a unifying and coherent framework for course development. This design approach systematically provides learning experiences that are realistic, relevant and generates stimulating opportunities to address these attributes. [25]. Similarly, the American Society for Engineering Education listed developing learning outcomes” as the first step for the process of redesigning engineering curriculum [26].

As such, our curriculum revamp started with a close examination of the course aims. What is missing is the ability of our graduates in applying chemical engineering principles in product design and development, and the infusion of soft skills such as oral communication, report writing and presentation, into the curriculum. They are presently taught in standalone modules. Core chemical engineering teachings are carried out in classroom very much the traditional lecturer-centred approach. Students still communicate poorly

or write badly despite the numerous presentations or assignments to hand in. Others, such as teamwork and critical thinking, although stressed in the curriculum, were not effectively covered in the various core chemical engineering modules. Often students are assumed to somehow “get it”; for example, how to think critically after working through several tutorial questions, or able to work in teams after assigning them in groups for a given assignment or laboratory experiment.

The CDIO initiative provides a structured framework for educating engineers. It reflected the desired attributes of engineers demanded by the industry. It emphasizes student-centred, outcome-based curriculum design that uses active learning to promote skills in conceiving, designing, implementing, and operating a product or systems using a life-cycle approach, along with soft skills such as teamwork, communication, various types of thinking, etc. It stressed teaching that is contextualized to reflect real-world environment. It also focuses on integrated learning, which serves to break down the “silos” in both the lecturers’ teaching and students’ learning. And it does so while maintaining that one does not need to increase curriculum hours to accommodate the changes to be made!

In planning its curriculum revamp, the team developed an appropriate CDIO Syllabus suitable for diploma-level engineering students. Subsequently, a CDIO Syllabus for chemical engineering was produced. Next, the team proceeded with the selection of three CDIO skills (namely, teamwork, communication, and personal skills and attitudes) for infusion into the DCHE curriculum. A set of underpinning knowledge for these three skills suitable for the polytechnic’s context were developed. A mass training for all academic staff was conducted, followed by a focused training on the underpinning knowledge for a group of trainers. A gap analysis was then carried out to identify shortfalls in the coverage of these three skills in the existing curriculum. Following that, modules that are most amenable to the infusion of various CDIO skills are selected.

We adopted a multi-prong approach. It was clear from the outset that the revised curriculum must contain two new modules, namely *Introduction to Chemical Engineering* and *Chemical Product Design*. It is also natural that our laboratory experiments, which are rich in hands-on experience, can be leveraged to provide the greatest opportunity and largest context on which infusion of CDIO skills can be initiated. With integration between various chemical engineering core modules being a requirement of the CDIO, another curriculum area identified as needing revamp is the *Plant Design and Project Evaluation*. Lastly, we acknowledge that there is a need to pilot with a core chemical engineering module to demonstrate how the selected CDIO skills can be infused into the module. In this case, *Chemical Reaction Engineering*, a Year 2 module taught by the author himself, is chosen.

To make room for these new modules in an already packed curriculum, it is necessary to make changes to existing modules. A workable solution, consistent with the concept of “Teach Less, Learn More” is by cutting some subject coverage to only the fundamentals, and educates

students that lifelong learning is the only key for progress and for filling in gaps that appear with practice [27]. The outcome of the revamp effort is a new course structure for the diploma. Brief discussions of the work done are described below.

Introduction to Chemical Engineering is a necessary module to be introduced to Year 1 students, as it served to introduce the discipline to the newly enrolled students fresh from their O-Levels. Many selected the course via online application without making the trip down to the institution for course counselling during enrolment exercise. Instead they merely relied on the web site or general information provided by course speakers during one of the school promotion talks prior to the O-Levels. The module introduces students to the chemical engineering profession, the chemical industry, roles and responsibilities of a chemical engineer; and supplemented with activities designed to offer some appreciation to the kind of job that a typical chemical engineer does. The aim is to give the students a greater appreciation at an early stage, of their course of study, and hopefully will kindle their spirit for learning chemical engineering. The module also introduces students to project work early in their course of study. Known in the CDIO parlance as design-build experience (DBE), it serves to interest students by challenging them to produce a simple product design and test out the design.

For *Chemical Product Design*, a year 2 module, we have decided to adopt the approach introduced by Moggridge and Cussler as it had much in common with Part 4 of the CDIO Syllabus. In their seminal paper, they elaborated on the expanded role of chemical engineers, emphasized on the necessity of to work in teams in a joint effort of product design and to participate in the whole enterprise from conception to manufacture. They outlined a simplified 4-step product design procedure that is already widely used in business development and manufacturing engineering. The procedure centred around the concepts of 'needs', 'ideas', 'selection', and 'manufacture' which mapped closely with the concepts of Conceive, Design, Implement and Operate of CDIO:

1. Needs: What needs should the product fill?
2. Ideas: What different products could fill this need?
3. Selection: Which ideas are the most promising?
4. Manufacture: How can we make the product and test it critically?

We also introduced into the *Chemical Product Design* module other CDIO requirements such as systems thinking, critical and creative thinking. A draft syllabus and the assessment criteria were prepared; to allow students to continue the effort in their final year project.

Cussler and Moggridge subsequently published the first textbook specifically addressing chemical product design [28], and a number of different universities now offered chemical product engineering-related courses, with more than 25 departments of chemical engineering in which this type of course is taught [29].

The introduction of *Chemical Product Design* also serves to provide the much needed extra dimension in chemical engineering education to move it away from just chemical process design [30], [31].

The introduction of *Chemical Product Design* necessarily leads to the revamp of the year-long module *Plant Design and Project Evaluation* which focused exclusively on the traditional chemical process design. The distinction between product and process design was made abundantly clear by Moggridge and Cussler. [22]. In *Plant Design and Project Evaluation*, students are required to complete a chemical plant design project whereby they are given a problem statement depicting a need to produce a given chemical product (typically a commodity chemical) and are required to work in team to come up with a process design to achieve the required production. Students typically carried out literature survey of available processes and upon selecting one, proceeded to carried out computer simulation for all the process flow streams and the equipment contained in the selected process, complete with an environmental and safety analysis of the design. Such plant design project does not satisfy the Conceive, Implement and Operate concepts of CDIO, as all the students experienced was computer simulation exercises!

The traditional focus on chemical process design, coupled with a largely modular course structure, meant that the curriculum is delivered via various modules each addressing a particular discipline of chemical engineering, relying on the integrative nature of plant design project to bring together the various concepts learnt. The obvious downside is that students tend to compartmentalize their learning, and are often unable to call up the relevant disciplinary knowledge in solving their plant design problem. It was also observed that students tend to rely of the computer simulation result to give them a design without much interpretation of the simulation results. Many also used trial-and-error in their simulation, hoping to get a converged answer by luck. It is further noted that chemical engineers typically carry out simulation and equipment design work for an individual piece of equipment as part of plant modification or upgrading work (for example, debottlenecking). It is very rare for diploma-level graduate to ever be involved in intensive plant-wide design work. Also, as the chemical processing industry reaches maturity, less chemical plant will be built.

The key issue here is therefore how to make the plant design exercise more meaningful to our students. As such, the module is now replaced by an innovative method of teaching that feature five modules spread over a 5-semester period, beginning in Year 1, and continued to completion in Year 3. The project started with a new module in Year 1 entitled *Introduction to Plant Design and Simulation* that teaches process flowsheeting, engineering symbols and drawings. Students were also taught how to use a design and simulation software such as ChemShare.

In this new approach, one lecturer is assigned to one class. The lecturer will follow the class as it progresses to the next stage of study. The group of lecturers will work closely with other module coordinators within the same stage to formulate activities that ties in with the overall plant design project. Students will gradually build-up their plant design by adding in various unit operations as well as applications in plant safety and environmental engineering etc in each semester when they undertake the relevant modules within

the same stage. For example, students will work on the heat exchanger aspect of their plant design when they studied *Heat Transfer and Equipment*. Skills such as teamwork and communication can also be designed into the new curriculum. Such an approach ties in well with the integrated learning and assessment requirement of the CDIO initiative.

Lastly, we focus on the revamp of *Chemical Reaction Engineering* to be the pilot module to showcase how various CDIO skills can be infused into a highly technical core chemical engineering module. The simple basis for the approach to revamp the module is based on extensive research that students learn best when they perceive a clear need to know the material being taught [32]. It is also clear that the best opportunity lies not in the classroom but in the laboratory, where students are to work in teams. Technical know-how and competences in soft skills are all integrated into the same learning environment. The CDIO paradigm here is that competences are context-dependent and should be learned and assessed in the technical context [33]. Soft skill such as communication is seen as contextualized competences rather than just a generic skill, and the teaching of communication should therefore be embedded in, and inseparable from, students' application of technical knowledge. The laboratory activities for this module are therefore revised using real-life work scenario so that students better appreciate the importance of these skills.

Revamp of the laboratory activities follows the student-centred Triangle of Course Design approach [34]. The author together with a senior education advisor reviewed all the module learning objectives and recast them in terms of the intended learning outcomes. The details of this work had been covered in a separate paper by the team [35].

Suffice to say the various learning tasks in this module, were all contextualized to provide an active, experiential learning experience for the students. The module also included a mini design-build experience where students are required to fabricate a simple reactor required for a given product conversion, and evaluate its performance by carrying out a laboratory experiment. A comprehensive student guide was also developed to accompany the module, complete with explanation of the desired learning attitudes, underpinning knowledge of the selected CDIO skills, along with a complete set of rubrics for used in the assessment of the required demonstration of the CDIO skills.

As the revised curriculum was only rolled out in April 2008, only some verbal feedbacks were obtained from students on the modules *Introduction to Chemical Engineering* and *Chemical Reaction Engineering*. Based on several de-brief sessions by the author, students in general appreciated the approach taken.

3 Issues and challenges, and how they were overcome

Without doubt, the biggest challenge faced is the short timeline for curriculum redesign before launching the new "CDIO-enabled" education model. Specifically the effort started in January 2007, after the team's trip to the 2006 CDIO Workshop and Conference in Montreal in November

2006. Senior Management had set the rollout date as April 2008. To this end, the decision is therefore made to proceed with the implementation without doing the stakeholder survey of the chemical industries in Singapore. Instead we inferred the requirements of stakeholders based on the feedback they provided to our questionnaire in our 5-year course review, which was conducted back in 2003.

Another issue of concern is staff buy-in. The CDIO Initiative must not be seen as another management fad that will come and go; something to pay lip service to without putting in serious effort to carry out any meaningful changes in the modules. Briefing sessions and workshops were conducted. The results of the gap analysis revealed significant disparity between the intended learning outcome as stipulated in the customized CDIO syllabus and what was being practiced in the individual modules. Additional effort is utilized to convince staff that the current revamp is an ongoing process in the spirit of continuous improvement, and the CDIO Initiative is no more than a framework that fits the objective of the revamp. Since it is an internationally-led effort by reputable universities, its sustainability should be assured. To encourage buy-in, lecturers are also encouraged to use the CDIO Initiative as the platform to conduct educational research as an avenue to career progression.

Available curriculum hours also posed a challenge. Traditional chemical engineering education in the polytechnic had closely mirrored university teaching. Topics covered reflected what a student will study at the university, albeit in a simplified version. The broad-based nature of traditional chemical engineering education also resulted in the need to cover much fundamental knowledge. One outcome is a curriculum packed with fundamental modules. This, plus the necessity to cover various stakeholder modules, leaves very little room to accommodate new technological development. Getting each lecturer to reduce his/her module content posed a big challenge. In the lecturer's mind, all current topics are individually self-classified as essential. If anything is to be done is to extend them! A major curriculum review exercise was carried out to identify modules to be revised, merged or otherwise removed, and more compact new modules were introduced.

Lack of laboratory space was another reservation expressed by many lecturers, thinking that new pilot plants are required to train students in these "new" skills of teamwork, communication, etc. Such doubts were built on the traditional approach to teaching and training in which many experiments and laboratory activities were designed pretty much to prove the theories taught in classrooms. With the revamp effort calling for a "new" approach to teaching and training, many lecturers naturally extended, in their own minds, the needs to have new facilities for new training. The result from the revamp of *Chemical Reaction Engineering* demonstrated conclusively that no additional workspaces are required. What is more important is how to weave into the existing laboratory sessions applications of various soft skills.

Staff competency is also of concern, especially with regards to the teaching of Chemical Product Design. Product design using chemical engineering principles is a relatively new concept for majority of chemical engineers. This is

because these products, which include performance chemicals, pharmaceuticals, formulated products such as household, beauty or personal care, food etc; have historically been the domain of chemists, material scientists and food technologists while chemical engineers focused on manufacturing processes [36]. However, the new paradigm emerging is that chemical engineers can have a significant role in the fashioning of the products themselves. Case studies need to be developed as a means of providing chemical engineers with an awareness of issues such as product innovation, consumer demand and sustainability [37]. Cussler and Wei [38] stressed that related educational changes will be evolutionary in nature rather than revolutionary as we expand our examples beyond those based on petrochemical feedstocks. Being a relatively new field in chemical engineering, there is indeed still a lack of case studies in chemical product design. The pool of current lecturers, being predominantly trained in classical chemical engineering, also lacked practical experience in chemical product design and development. Training in this area is of utmost importance to the DCHE CMT.

Lastly, improvement is required in the way many module syllabi are written. Based on Bloom's taxonomy, many existing syllabi for chemical engineering were mainly written at knowledge and comprehension level rather than more performance-outcome-based. Many lecturers do not fully grasp the concept of outcome-based education and hence had difficulty with writing syllabi in terms of learning outcomes. A related issue is that of assessments. There is an apparent disconnection between module syllabi and choice of assessment methods and what is being assessed. Often assessments are prepared largely independent of what is being written in the syllabi. Students are often tested on knowledge and understanding, rather than competency to perform a given task. This is one big area that the CMT expects most lecturers will have problems in. Difficulty also existed in assessment of soft skills, as lecturers tend to focus only on the technical content of students' output. Part of the reason was the lack of time, another being the lecturers themselves do not know "what to look for". Another assessment-related challenge is that many lecturers are also new to the concept of integrated assessment [39]. More staff development workshop may be needed to address this issue.

4 Key learning points

A key learning point from the revamp effort, especially on infusion of CDIO skills into a core technical module such as *Chemical Reaction Engineering*, is that one can leverage on existing laboratory sessions without incurring additional curriculum hours. Each of the experiments requires three hours, and two lecturers were deployed full-time for the entire duration of the session. The execution of this module, however, is more the exception than the norm. Other chemical engineering laboratory sessions typically employ one lecturer for the entire duration of the session, plus an additional lecturer to help out within the first hour (for a 3-hour experiment) or two hours (for a 4-hour experiment). Although there is no net increase in curriculum hours,

certainly staff workload will increase if two lecturers are deployed full-time for all laboratory experiments.

To achieve effective integration of curriculum, especially with the modular course structure, it is important that each lecturer knows what the other lecturers are teaching. Often there is a lack of communication between lecturers themselves! The practice of rotating module teaching using different lecturers after a few semesters will help facilitate common understanding between them.

The use of a pilot module like *Chemical Reaction Engineering* is important as it provided the author with first-hand experience how to go about executing the necessary revamp. The result can serve as a useful 'template' to illustrate how the infusion of various soft skills can be achieved in practice. This will serve to allay the fears of many lecturers of possible increased curriculum hours that such curricular revamp entails, and also build confidence in how to effectively assess effectiveness of non-technical skills such as communication and teamwork.

Another lesson learnt is that it may not be wise to skip the stakeholder analysis, at least on the part of our own lecturers! Just as a 'top down' approach using graduate attributes as the output requirements and driver for curriculum development is important, a 'bottom up' approach to ownership and sustainability of the curriculum development, delivery and quality control is equally essential. The results from the gap analysis showed varied level of understanding among the lecturers, despite the workshops and briefings. Gap analysis turned out to be a time-consuming process, and some iteration is required before an acceptable outcome is attained. Some lecturers appear more or less to get it, but others apparently do not. Retrospectively, by going through with the stakeholder survey exercise, we could have instilled a stronger sense of ownership among the lecturers and hence greater buy-in from them [40].

The initial design of the gap analysis survey is very important. Each lecturer is encouraged to detail the actions taken in the module to infuse a particular CDIO skill. The gap analysis survey has helped to identify good practices and serve as an important document for common learning and to ensure continuity of teaching approach adopted and inculcation of desired learning behaviour when teaching is passed from one lecturer to another. Inclusion of the gap analysis is now instituted as one of the "handover checklist" items accompanying any module handover. This will also ensure the continuity of the CDIO-driven revamp when more CDIO skills are chosen for infusion.

The author also finds that working one-to-one with an education advisor is very effective at eliciting the hidden or implied learning objectives desired by the module coordinator but not verbalised satisfactorily in written form in the specific learning objectives. Probing questions from the education advisor can help the lecturer crystallize the rationale behind a stated learning objective, the revision of which can lead to a much clearer learning outcome. It becomes apparent that one should write learning outcomes in clear and appropriate terms.

Lastly, using an outcome-based approach in assessment of learning outcome, can help promote clearer and creative

thinking in curriculum development. It is again the experience of the author that, on several occasions, new ideas emerged during brainstorming sessions to overcome a particular problem with the implementation plan. In one instance, the team faced with the possible clash of usage of equipment with another diploma. After some deliberations, it struck the team that the desired learning outcome can be achieved by other means, and in this case by making use of an otherwise mothballed pilot plant that just sat there occupying precious laboratory space and gathering dust.

5 The path forward

We are just at the beginning of the curriculum revamp. With the roll-out of the CDIO-enabled curriculum, we will continue to monitor student performance and obtain feedback from them on its. The DCHE CMT will continue to work with our educational advisors to carry out revision of the assessment methods and conduct various evaluations of student learning via questionnaires, interviews, etc.

At the micro level, more core modules other than *Chemical Reaction Engineering* will be targeted for infusion of teamwork, communication, plus personal skills and attitudes as well as greater cross-module integration. Additional CDIO skills will also be selected for infusion, and relevant workshops will be conducted for all lecturers. Gap analysis will be performed for the newly selected skills. For new modules, appropriate CDIO skills and assessment will be designed into the modules right from the beginning. To encourage more buy-in, sharing sessions will be conducted, where lecturers with good practices can share the work done. This will also convince everyone that the CDIO Initiative is for the long haul, and not another educational revamp in passing.

Continuous monitoring of implementation of the *Chemical Product Design* is necessary as the field evolves. It is already fast gaining momentum in the chemical engineering community, already been touted as the so-called “third paradigm” of chemical engineering [41]. The EFCE recommended that “...some knowledge of ‘product engineering’ in the common core in order to reflect the increasing importance of modern materials science” [42]. The importance can be witnessed by the focus given to the topic at international conferences, such as the AIChE 2008 Process Engineering Symposium: Chemical Product Engineering, and CHEMPOR 2008; the 10th International Chemical and Biological Engineering Conference.

Some challenges remained, for example, in identifying raw materials, intermediates and final compounds that will make an impact on the final products and formulations [43]. Related developments in green engineering, process intensification, micro-scale processing etc are all converging on chemical product engineering, along with more traditional chemical process design. Integration of product design with process design will serve as the “interfacial discipline” of the future, bridging science and engineering in the multi-disciplinary environments where new technologies will be brought into being [44]. A new structure for chemical product engineering was recently proposed by Costa et al

[29], which encompass chemical product design and its integration with process design using a multi-scale perspective and a multi-faceted, approach.

Notwithstanding the above, it must be borne in mind that what we are doing here has to be properly scoped within the requirement of a diploma-level education. As chemical product engineering spans a multi-scale perspective, it is important that we cover what is appropriate at the diploma-level. The CMT concluded that coverage for DCHE is best carried out mainly at the meso-scale and micro-scale [45], focusing on translating a workable idea into a viable product with commercialization potential. More fundamental research in product design and in-depth technical analysis (for examples: nano-scale characterization, computational fluid dynamics, property estimation, modeling and programming, etc) are best left to the universities.

More fine-tuning of the *Chemical Product Design* module can be expected as more lecturers become familiar with the concept, and gain experience with the process. The DCHE CMT also anticipated the necessity of the introduction of a new module that teaches more “exotic” unit operations such as emulsification, spray cooling, extrusion, coating and granulation, which are more relevant to product design and development [46]. It can also be expected that some backward integration will be contemplated to introduce the chemical product design concept in Year 1 in a related module on innovation, design and enterprise.

At the macro level, the CMT will continue to study the changes that is affecting the chemical engineering industry in general, and in the education of chemical engineers in particular vis-à-vis the ongoing reform in engineering education [47], [48]. Already gaining accelerated attention is education on sustainable development. The chemical engineering profession had staked its position to support sustainable development following the Melbourne Communiqué [49]. The US National Research Council has identified sustainability education as one of the eight Grand Challenges confronting the chemical industry [50]. IChemE further noted that chemical engineering is presented with “a moment of opportunity” to tackle the issue of sustainable development and subsequently listed sustainability as one of the six priority topics of focus in its Roadmap [51], [52].

Batterham [53] posed the question of whether chemical engineering graduates are prepared to face this challenge. The very notion of sustainable development will require new approaches in a number of areas. Innovation at all levels and in all fields of activity is the most effective instrument for ensuring that the economic, and environmental goals, as well as those of society, are being advanced [54]. The role of chemical engineers will no doubt take on another new dimension. The introduction of *Chemical Product Design* in the curriculum is timely as product design has been identified as one of the engineering tools that form the architecture for sustainable development [55]. Grossmann [56] emphasized that chemical engineers need to adopt broader approaches to the life cycle assessment of products and processes in order to predict more accurately their long-term sustainability. With its focus of life-cycle analysis, the DCHE CMT believed that the CDIO approach, with its Conceive, Design, Implement,

Operate framework, lends itself readily to incorporate the requirement of sustainable development into chemical engineering curriculum. Hence the CMT is confident that its graduates will be able to play a proactive role in the development of new products that meet the requirement of sustainability.

Given the ever-broadening of roles of chemical engineers, it is clear that any attempt to cover all “relevant” subject matters – core chemical engineering or otherwise – will prove futile. Much has been said about the “ideal” content of a chemical engineering core curriculum. At one extreme, Cussler et al [57] even proposed a number of potentially controversial changes such as dropping the mandatory aspect of a capstone process design course, and a reduction in teaching of thermodynamics. Notwithstanding the above, efforts are already underway in an attempt to “standardize” the teaching of chemical engineering in the universities. In Europe, effort is already underway as part of the harmonization effort under the Bologna Declaration of 1999. Molzahn [58] further argued that the Bologna Process is offering new opportunities for chemical engineering to re-invent itself. Armstrong [59] argued that the current core content of chemical engineering was developed a long time ago and called for the re-examination of what constitute the core. Favre et al [60] proposed a framework and content for a teaching program on chemical product engineering that has been implemented and awaiting feedback from the industry. Similarly, the “Frontiers” initiative of MIT mentioned earlier is also working towards the same direction. For all these developments, there appears to be general consensus that a chemical engineering program should maintain some flexibility in its offering [61].

For the longer term, the DCHE CMT can make use of a “Universal Chemical Engineering Degree” model by Bryne [20] which consists of a chemical engineering core supplemented by secondary options. The model offers flexibility in that the core content is not necessarily fixed. Similarly, the relative weight or importance of the supplementary options is not defined. The team will critically examine what would constitute the “right mix” of chemical engineering course content in the Polytechnic’s own context. We will review again its current course structure to assess its appropriateness to suit developments within the polytechnic, as well as to address the abovementioned challenges. A possibility for future DCHE curriculum may evolve into one with several areas of concentrations, such as refinery and petrochemicals, pharmaceutical and bioprocessing, environmental and sustainable development (which include clean energy), as well as engineering management. It is therefore can be expected that the course structure will be changed again in the near future.

6 Conclusions

The Diploma in Chemical Engineering is indeed in turbulent yet exciting times. With the multi-prong approach adopted, the CDIO framework will serve the course well into the foreseeable future with the ongoing curriculum redesign effort. The lessons learnt from the initial phase of curriculum

revamp are useful to help fine-tune subsequent change effort. Given all the prevalent developments, there is no doubt that our graduates need to be equipped with the necessary skills to handle the challenges that confront the chemical engineering profession. Indeed, a recent review by Cobb et al [62] concluded that the description of what really is a chemical engineering continues to evolve – and that chemical engineers must be life-long learners.

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